

Modeling Physiological Needs

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***Abstract*—Human behavior is constrained, and partly motivated, by reoccurring conditions that must be met to ensure survival. In this paper, we focus on how those conditions arise through a model of physiological needs. This model is designed to be suitable for study and useful for automated reasoning. We explore the model, delve into our methodology, and highlight its value and practical significance. We conducted a review of relevant literature and chose to expand on the MAGE model. We justify the use of levels of intensity, explain why certain needs were selected to be modeled, what types of models we decided to search for, how models are combined, and introduce helper models for building scenarios. A typical day is simulated and results are discussed with their implications for further research. We undertake an evaluation to ascertain the efficacy of the model, and assess the research methodology underpinning its development. We conclude by outlining a list of possible improvements for the model and discussing the role of reasoning.**

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation for the problem

Imagine a philosopher is sitting on a rock when a particular quandary occurs to them which is more intriguing than anything. It becomes the only object of their focus, and so they sit there unmoving as seasons roll one into the other. The problem is unsolvable. Forever passes and they sit there, still, in the same position they started in. This situation is impossible. In the world we live in, they would be dead.

The world as understood by human consideration is usually a very full one. Many goals, concerns, and interests must be balanced and chosen between at any given time. Situations involving total focus on a singular task, such as during problem solving and in social activities, can only last uninterrupted for a short period of time. The most absolute and unavoidable cause of interruption seems to be the need for survival. Even the most ensnared philosopher caught in the edifice of their reasoning must take breaks and focus on surviving in the world around them, else they would face extinction. An interesting computational property is ensured by this state of affairs, the loops humans recreate in their behavior must be compatible with the loops of satisfying the reoccurring conditions needed to survive. Additionally, it seems intuitive to presume that the “higher” loops of human motivation may draw further value from their ability to aid survival. For example, a mutually beneficial friendship which makes use of

reciprocity may find itself stronger if what is exchanged helps with surviving, such as the sharing of food, water, shelter, etc. Thus, practical planning with human participants would do well to model these conditions in order to evaluate and inquire about improvements for the feasibility or acceptability of a course of action, especially those that continue indefinitely.

B. Breaking the problem into manageable parts

A roadblock for such a model is that the need to survive is far too general a problem to tackle without putting a great deal of effort into its definition. To begin with, it may be broken down into two distinct forms, each of a considerably different nature, which risk conflation and confusion. The first is the intellectualized need to survive where reason and intuition are used to apprehend the danger of a situation and attempt to avert it. This involves a conceptual understanding of life, death, and the decisions required to survive. Additionally, it may manifest in the weight of arguments involving and questioning the value and feasibility of more personal and intellectual needs. These other needs might often operate independent of concerns for survival, but are grounded by them to avoid maintaining disastrous convictions. The second form is physiological and its relation to survival is implicit involving multiple needs for carrying out specific actions that correlate with not dying, such as sleeping, eating, and generally those that help to restore homeostasis. Simply put, the second form consists of feelings that help with surviving and the first form, the application of knowledge which often uses those feelings. We take for granted that the second physiological form precedes reasoning and so we restrict our scope to it as the fundamental foundation of a working model of human needs. This is a pragmatic choice, the intellectual form cannot be confidently developed into an adequate model without physiological needs as grounding, and so they are taken as a starting place.

C. Following a useful goal

Finally, we must temper our ambitions to what we can theoretically and practically achieve. It should be made clear from the beginning that a perfectly accurate and universally applicable model of physiological needs is not our goal. Humans may be affected in sophisticated ways across age, weight, height, sex, and innumerable physical and psychological differences that the authors do not have

the resources to delicately respond to. Such a task might be more a field of study than a particular model. Instead, our goal is an intelligible model whose parameters are clear and which can easily be studied, adapted, and improved upon for new purposes. We hope that the model can be further refined by usage in larger systems. Potential applications include the following:

- 1) Interactive agents which can decide when to ask appropriate questions;
- 2) Planning systems that can infer new goals given only facts;
- 3) Time-bound automated reasoners that can shift attention to different objectives;
- 4) Simulating social networks developed in natural situations;
- 5) A source of motivation within cognitive architectures.

II. BACKGROUND

A. *Hints on studying physiological needs*

Perhaps the most famous model of needs is Maslow's hierarchy [1]. This model is neither mathematical nor computational, but instead an informal classification of types of needs and how those types interact. It has often been misrepresented as the simple statement that lower needs must be met prior to satisfying higher needs. This is only the most extreme case of many; the initial paper itself presents the normal situation as one in which needs are often partially met and actions meet multiple needs on multiple levels. Most importantly for our model, the paper begins with an extended discussion about physiological needs. The key points we shall use here are that physiological needs are unusual compared to other needs because they are isolable and localizable somatically. What this means is that individual physiological needs can be separated, studied, and defined independently using measurable information about the body as well as located specifically within the body.

B. *Counterpoint against uselessness of the task*

A further point looming over almost all works commenting on physiological needs, as introduced in Maslow's paper, is the futility of making a list of fundamental physiological needs. The reason given is that such a list can be extended indefinitely depending on the chosen degree of specificity. We do not argue one way or another that such a list can or cannot be indefinitely extended. We do, however, take issue with such a list being useless and, in particular, because one can choose a different level of specificity. This is because we can choose a specificity that is practically useful, one which allows generating typical planned behavior for healthy adults in everyday situations using measurable physical variables to determine felt need intensities.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW & RELATED WORK

A. *Initial models*

The first project we looked at in order to develop a model of needs was need-based AI used in game programming [2]. This

model is a clever approach used for generating spontaneous behavior in virtual agents in video games, such as The Sims. Needs are represented as numeric values between 0 and 100 which decay over time, requiring actions to keep the agent healthy. What makes the approach novel is that virtual objects provide the agents with "advertisements" of how they might help meet a need. This allows a wide variety of situations to be represented by creating new objects rather than modifying the agent.

The second project was designed around using needs to schedule daily-activities [3]. What made this project unique was its focus on the habitual nature of needs and their explicit dependence on time. For example, instead of only having needs that evolve independently of when a situation is started, some needs are tied to the time of day or day of the week. This can be seen in how the timing of breakfast, lunch, and dinner are used to initiate the increase of the hunger need.

Ultimately, we chose to abandon these approaches as the task of how to define needs was left under-specified. It was hard to imagine how to extend these models as they did not contain the sophistication needed to reflect the interesting feature of real-life needs. In particular, no attempt at a plausible model of the digestive system was made. This is unfortunate as much of everyday life is determined by the complexities of this system in particular.

B. *Primary inspiration*

Our model is based on the MAGE model as described in its paper [4]. This model makes use of medical research to justify its choice of parameters, making it a suitable foundation to build upon. It also introduces the use of six levels of need intensity and their role in action selection. It presents models to help determine thirst, hunger, sleep, and urination. The body-water model and bladder model are kept almost identical in our model. The sleep model [5] mentioned in MAGE was not implemented in their project. However, we have implemented it and also modified it, so a sleeping time of 11 PM has an intensity of a strong need. The MAGE hunger model is based on calculating daily calories, which we have replaced almost entirely, but we have kept how it absorbs water from ingested food. The original model is not particularly realistic as it assumes no energy reserves, but more importantly, everyday hunger is better determined by a combination of hormones, stomach fullness, and habitual patterns. Instead, we use a food intake model [6] and base need intensity on "appetite." Additionally, we add a rectum model which we feel necessary for conceptual completeness being a solid waste counterpart to the bladder model's liquid waste. Thermal comfort was added as well, using pythermalcomfort [7] which fortunately also uses a similar six-point scale for discomfort for hot and cold temperatures. Modelling thermal comfort, hunger, thirst, sleepiness, and need to urinate and defecate allows our model to cover the most obvious concerns for everyday survival. The most substantial change, however, has been how we have grounded the meaning of need intensities in behavior. MAGE only invokes actions when an

involuntary physiological response occurs, which only happens at the maximum need intensity. Our model, by contrast, has a control model for handling voluntary and spontaneous actions as well along with considering conditions for invoking actions at all levels of intensity. Tools for using and modifying these models along with a system for controlling and instantiating circumstances have also been developed which are elaborated on next.

IV. METHODOLOGY & DESIGN

A. *Justifying levels of intensity for needs*

A primary objective for our model was that it should be conducive to building applications, and in particular automated reasoners. To accomplish this task, we model need intensity in terms of six discrete levels. This was a feature introduced by MAGE and to some extent pythermalcomfort, but we shall justify it here as it might be contentious. Designing rules that respond to continuous values can be extremely difficult as it is hard to get a grasp on what any particular value means. As a result, even though we have intuitions about our needs, it is unclear how to formalize them. By using discrete levels whose meanings are clearly defined, we hope to get around this issue. Additionally, when two needs are close in magnitude, a great deal of effort is often spent trying to figure out which need to meet first. We hope to allow reasoners to capture this by noticing when two needs are on the same level. This means having too many levels restricts our ability to have levels with clear meaning and capture needs being close in magnitude. However, we would like to have many levels to capture the subtlety of differences in need intensity and in the extreme case approximate need intensities if they really are continuous. As a result, a compromise is sought of having neither too few nor too many levels. The solution we have chosen is to give each level a specific role in generating behavior and see that the six levels defined by MAGE are adequate. In a sense, we develop a “proto-reasoner” called the control model that already uses need intensities to make decisions and so gives semantic meaning to the levels and serves as an example for writing more flexible reasoners.

B. *Identifying needs to model*

As mentioned earlier, we have chosen to make use of a level of specificity that is practical for planning everyday behavior. This suggests a particular time scale to operate in. Needs that require too quick a response do not benefit much from extensive planning. Needs that operate on too long a time scale will have factors that change in unpredictable ways due to the extended duration, making it harder to consider clear looping conditions that must be ensured for survival. As a result, we focus on everyday needs that operate on the minute to hour time scale. These needs have the largest influence on planning one’s day: heating, cooling, hunger, thirst, sleep, urination, and defecation. Unfortunately, as a result, we must put on hold modeling needs such as air hunger [8].

C. *Searching for models*

To cover a wide array of situations and provide stronger justification for results, computational and mathematical models were sought out that were developed based on medical research. This task proved to be challenging, as only a limited number of models satisfied all of these criteria. The food intake model met these criteria, but was not a need model, and so had to be modified by observing the ranges of values appetite took on to assign appropriate need intensity levels. There was no model of defecation, but there was medical research on it, so it was constructed from several papers. Need intensities were estimated from two papers on rectal filling and the urge to defecate which had similar results [9] [10]. Additionally, papers were used to estimate the water content and density of feces [11] along with the frequency of defecation [12]. The act is assumed to take 10 minutes.

D. *Combining models*

Earlier, Maslow had mentioned that physiological needs were localizable somatically and isolable. For the most part, this is true in our model. Models for body components, such as the stomach, rectum, and water content are each responsible for individual needs. As one might expect, there is quite a bit of connection between different organs. For example, the absorbed water in the stomach model is added to the body-water model. The primary way models interact is by producing and taking in substances produced by other models. Models can interact in indirect ways as well, such as causing an action to be performed that changes the behavior of another model. This can be seen in how sleeping reduces glucose uptake in the stomach model slowing the rate of hunger. The advantage of simulating multiple needs is that they can conceptually complete each other, providing ways of sourcing external variables.

E. *Helper models*

In order for a model of needs to be useful and scientifically valuable, it is essential to establish a reliable methodology for testing its validity as well as construct the situations that we would like to see the model respond to. Ideally, this should be accomplished by a reasoning system or specification language. Here, we leverage a selection of preliminary models for controlling and specifying situations. The exercise model keeps track of metabolic rate and when exercise can occur and its intensity. The feeding model presents what food and beverages are available at different times of the day, such as breakfast, lunch, dinner, dessert, and snacking in between meals. The dresser model keeps track of accessible clothing which an agent can wear to provide insulation for thermal comfort. The environment model keeps track of general environmental factors, such as time of day, light level, humidity, and air speed.

V. RESULTS

A typical day has been simulated with the results shown in Figure 1. A time-step of two minutes has been chosen

Fig. 1. Need intensities and behavior generated over a 24 hour period

following the food intake model. At each time-step, behavior is plotted on the top graph by assigning to each action 1 if it is being performed and 0 otherwise. Need intensity is also plotted at each time-step on the bottom graph following the six-point scale, although here the highest the intensity reaches is three which corresponds to a strong need.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of results

The model results appear to be fairly realistic, but with several points that could be improved upon. The agent wakes up around 6:30 AM and goes to sleep around 11 PM as expected. Earlier simulations of multiple days after altering light to change circadian rhythm suggest that the sleep model is robust. Drinking continues throughout the day since thirst is considered a very easy need to satisfy. If no conflicting actions are occurring and there is any degree of thirst, the agent will drink. Due to a lack of data on times for drinking different beverages and a digestion model for drinking, beverages are consumed entirely in one time-step and their water is absorbed instantaneously. As a result, drinking stops once a beverage has been consumed that sets the body’s water level above its normal level. It might be better to somewhat exceed the normal body’s water level to reduce how quickly the need reoccurs. Additionally, the agent only urinates once per day which seems too low. Surpassing the normal body’s water level may help get a more accurate estimate. Longer periods of eating for breakfast, lunch, dinner, and dessert can be seen along with short periods for snacks which is a promising pattern. The food intake model is probabilistic and, as a result, simulated days can be quite different with some even skipping meals due to increased snacking. This is considered acceptable since this

occurs in reality as well. When multiple days are simulated without eating, appetite in the food intake model does not increase past the first day. We take this to mean intense hunger cannot be represented by the model. Digested food enters the rectum immediately after leaving the stomach, however, there should be a wait time for the time spent in the intestines. This can be seen in defecation occurring too quickly after large meals. It is also assumed that all carbohydrates are absorbed, which gives more realistic results for defecation than if none is absorbed. Defecation occurs three times per day which is a somewhat realistic result [13]; when none is absorbed, defecation can occur six times. The only absorbed substances from food are water and carbohydrates with the rest becoming feces. Water is also consumed in producing feces. With a better model of nutrient absorption, less feces may be produced using less water, hopefully giving more accurate results for both defecation and urination.

B. Implications for research

Work still remains on modeling physiological needs; nevertheless, the task has undergone substantial refinement, leading to more well-defined objectives. Since much about the physiological mechanisms for determining need intensity have been specified, it is easier to propose improvements to the model. Most of the limitations expressed here appear to be solvable with further research. Despite the improvements that can be made, the results are still plausible with no actions being repeated too often or not occurring when they should in the single day simulations. Consequently, it is not premature to build upon the existing model in its current state. Extending the model with new needs may not pose an arduous endeavor as the needs modeled agree with Maslow’s claim of being isolate, thus further needs might be modeled in the same way. Additionally, just as the rectum model is based on the bladder model, new needs might re-use techniques from already-modeled needs. The most interesting prospect, however, is how to integrate actions pertaining to newly-introduced needs into the control model. By assigning levels of intensity to a need and generating behavior from the control model, needs can be analyzed relative to others and thus their properties more fully elucidated. In this way, the weight of higher needs might even be able to be discerned.

VII. CONCLUSION

Were we successful in constructing an intelligible model of physiological needs? Yes. However, it is hard to disregard the pending tasks that still remain. It is an adequate working model and, as far as we are aware, the most complete model of physiological needs developed so far. Despite this, it is of greater excitement to imagine what the model may look like once refined. We do believe the model succeeds particularly well, however, in being intelligible. The use of intensity levels and the control model for behavior have led to substantial clarity by introducing a clear unit of need and bringing all code for making decisions into one model.

The exploration of physiological needs proved to be an intriguing endeavor. Despite widespread knowledge of Maslow's hierarchy placing physiological needs as the most basic, there is surprisingly little on physiological needs that has been mathematically or computationally formalized. Much of what has been formalized is far more focused on needs abstracted from their concrete functions, but needs cannot be treated this way, since their conceptual value lies in their distinct nature. For example, hunger is interesting in how it differs from sleep because different types of actions are required to satisfy them, leading to a system of action with sophisticated features. As a result, our research consisted in large part of searching for usable models. When we encountered the MAGE model, we were impressed by its use of medical research to justify its choices that we required every other model we used to be of the same calibre of quality. When we implemented these models in programming, it proved crucial to consider how to test them and what type of interface a computational model of needs should have as a software library. In the process, we re-wrote much of the project's code multiple times due to being overwhelmed at its complexity and often perplexed at how it functioned. This would lead to developing the control model to make it clear how actions are performed. The concept of action evolved organically to where actions could be voluntary, involuntary, spontaneous, or easy. Additionally, actions are dynamic being continued, disrupted, prevented, simultaneous, and chosen. We consider "working out the conditions for how actions are performed in the control model" to be the key contribution of this research.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

The following are proposed future work avenues to improve the utility of a model of physiological needs:

- 1) An improved model of digestion and nutrition:
 - Absorption of more nutrients than glucose
 - Proper time for digested food to reach rectum
 - Proper time for water absorption for drink and food
 - Influence of food temperature on thermal comfort
 - Exhaustion of eating similar nutrients
 - Intense hunger modeling
- 2) A library for constructing new situations:
 - Preset model objects for times of day, stomach contents, bladder fullness, sleepiness, meals, etc.
 - Ability to set parameters of a model to be between two preset models
 - A set of situations designed to test the simulation capabilities of the model whose components might be re-used in other situations
 - "Default" models that can be used to abstract over periods of time by representing normal changes in a situation
- 3) Time sensitivity to thermal changes using core temperature.

Additionally, the use of reasoning within the model could lead to some interesting systems. Individual components of the model may be ignored and their influences replaced with the result of a reasoning process to account for a lack of information, unusual situations, and predictable inaccuracies in a component. Reason as a "band-aid" to the intuition provided from modeling could allow for systems that are pragmatically competent and flexible in their modification. Models which overemphasize their concerns may still prove useful as they bring awareness to important aspects of a situation that may be better handled by reasoning or asking a user questions to ascertain useful information.

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